

Weighted Sum-of-Trees Model for Clustered Data

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Abstract

Clustered data, which arise when observations are nested within groups, are incredibly common in clinical, education, and social science research. Traditionally, a linear mixed model, which includes random effects to account for within-group correlation, would be used to model the observed data and make new predictions on unseen data. Some work has been done to extend the mixed model approach beyond linear regression into more complex and non-parametric models, such as decision trees and random forests. However, existing methods are limited to using the global fixed effects for prediction on data from out-of-sample groups, effectively assuming that all clusters share a common outcome model. We propose a lightweight sum-of-trees model in which we learn a decision tree for each sample group. We combine the predictions from these trees using weights so that out-of-sample group predictions are more closely aligned with the most similar groups in the training data. This strategy also allows for inference on the similarity across groups in the outcome prediction model, as the unique tree structures and variable importances for each group can be directly compared. We show our model outperforms traditional decision trees and random forests in a variety of simulation settings. Finally, we showcase our method on two existing data sets: the Hospital Doctor Patient data set, a synthetic benchmark data set where patients are grouped by treating physician and hospital, and real-world data from the sarcoma cohort of The Cancer Genome Atlas, where patient samples are grouped by sarcoma subtype.

Key Words: Decision trees, random forest, mixed effects modeling, weighted ensemble, clustered data

1 Introduction

The decision tree is one of the most widely used machine learning methods. Its most popular implementation, the Classification and Regression Tree (CART) algorithm, was introduced by Breiman (1998). Though decision trees are weak predictors by themselves, they have been shown to perform incredibly well when used in an ensemble, as in a random forest (RF) or boosting model. A random forest fits trees in parallel using a bootstrapping technique to reduce overall model variance (Breiman, 2001), while boosting fits sequential trees to residuals to reduce bias (Hastie et al., 2009). Decision trees and their extensions are also tolerant of missing data, interpretable, robust against collinearity, and have built-in feature selection.

In clinical, education, and social science research, grouped data are incredibly common. For example, in educational research, students may be grouped within classrooms or schools. In biomedical research, patients may be grouped within hospitals or by disease subtype. In these cases, the observations can no longer be considered independent due to the within-group, or intraclass, correlations (Jiang and Nguyen, 2007). While independence among observations is not always a rigid assumption of decision trees and other machine learning models, accounting for the grouping structure during model construction can improve predictive performance. Handling of the grouped observations becomes especially important when predicting outcomes for observations that belong to groups outside of our training sample. For example, we may want to make predictions for students attending schools that were not included in our training data set.

Clustered data are just one example of non-independent data structures, which are typically handled using mixed effects models. Mixed effects refer to the idea that some associations, known as fixed effects, share a consistent pattern across the population, while other attributes of the data have a random effect on the outcome, leading to correlation across multiple observations from a unit such as individual patients or doctors. Some work has been done to incorporate mixed effects into tree-based models for clustered or longitudinal data (Hajjem et al., 2011; Spanbauer and Sparapani, 2021). However, existing methods suffer from limitations inherent in mixed effects models themselves. Mainly, out-of-sample prediction for mixed models uses only the fixed effects, as the random effects cannot be learned with no training data from those groups. Many methods also use a rigid additive structure for combining the fixed and random effects, similar to a linear mixed model, which takes away from the flexibility of decision trees.

In Section 1.1, we discuss existing tree-based models for clustered data and their limitations. In Section 2, we introduce a lightweight method that learns a unique decision tree for each group. Predictions for out-of-sample groups are then calculated as a weighted linear combination of predictions from the decision trees learned from groups in the training data. In Section 3.1, we highlight simulation studies that show that our method outperforms standard decision trees, random forests, and linear mixed models across a range of settings. Finally, in Section 3.2, we show that our method performs competitively on synthetic benchmark and real data applications.

1.1 Background on Existing Methods

Generalized linear mixed models (GLMM) are the most standard approach for settings with clustered data. In a GLMM, we fit the model: $g(\mathbb{E}[y|X]) = X\beta + Z\alpha$, where $g(\cdot)$ represents the link function, y corresponds to the outcome variable, X represents the design matrix for the fixed effects, and Z is the design matrix for the random effects (Breslow and Clayton, 1993). As in standard linear models, GLMMs assume additive linear effects, which may be overly simplistic and lead to poor performance on complex data sets where there may be predictors with extreme values, non-linear effects, interactions, or other deviations from the assumptions of the linear model structure.

Mixed effects regression trees (MERT, Hajjem et al., 2011), use an Expectation Maximization (EM) approach to iteratively fit the model $y = f(X) + Z\alpha + \varepsilon$. The fixed effects $f(X)$ are fit using a regression tree, followed by an update fitting the random effects using standard techniques. MERT has been extended to forests using a bootstrapping technique (Hajjem et al., 2014). Currently, there are no extensions of MERT addressing categorical outcome data.

The MERT approach has a number of limitations. First, as in a standard GLMM model, the random part $Z\alpha$ is strictly linear and additive. It also assumes observations in different clusters are independent, though this is often not the case. Furthermore, the fixed and random effects are estimated separately, which means that any interaction between fixed and random effects is precluded. Finally, as with standard mixed models, MERT can only use the fixed effects to make out-of-sample predictions.

In the Bayesian framework, Bayesian Additive Regression Trees (BART) were originally proposed by [Chipman et al. \(2010\)](#). [Spanbauer and Sparapani \(2021\)](#) proposed mixedBART as an extension to BART that can handle mixed effects. Similar to both GLMMs and MERT, they fit an additive model, where fixed effects and random effects are fit sequentially and separately via BART and a Bayesian mixed model, respectively. Here, the Bayesian framework is quite convenient, as these two approaches can easily be integrated into alternating steps of the MCMC algorithm.

Case-specific random forests (CSRFs, [Xu et al., 2016](#)) build a unique random forest for each new point in the test dataset. Instead of the traditional bootstrap technique, with a uniform selection probability on each observation, larger weights are assigned to points which are closer to the test case. One significant downside to this approach is the computational complexity and time needed to build a new random forest for each sample in the test data set. This method also does not directly account for mixed effects, but nevertheless could be useful in settings with mixed effects present.

Finally, [De Jong et al. \(2021\)](#) propose internal-external cross validation, which incorporates the clustered structure into drawing training vs validation vs test datasets, and picks the model that performs best on most samples out of group. However, still only one output model is chosen.

2 Methods

2.1 Proposed Approach

We now describe our proposed approach for flexible prediction on clustered data. In developing our method, we are particularly interested in the challenge of obtaining predictions for observations that do not belong to groups seen in the training data.

Let \mathbf{X} represent an $n \times p$ matrix corresponding to n observations on p features, and Y be an $n \times 1$ column vector of outcomes. In our training dataset, each observation comes from one of $k = 1, 2, \dots, K$ known groups or clusters, such that the observations within each cluster are correlated. We call the $n \times 1$ column vector of group assignments C . The testing dataset follows the same structure, except our groups are now indexed $m = 1, 2, \dots, M$. Here, we focus on settings where the groups in the test data fall outside groups encountered in the training dataset.

Our method proceeds in two stages. First, we construct a classification model $f : \mathbf{X} \rightarrow C$ on the training data. Using this approach, each test observation has a vector of prediction probabilities associated with belonging to each of the K groups. We take the output probabilities of belonging to a certain class and call them weights $w = (w_1, \dots, w_K)$. We interpret these weights as a similarity metric for measuring the closeness of a test data point X_t to groups in the training data considering only the \mathbf{X} feature space. If there is more than one observation in an unseen group m , we average the similarity weights across the group and use that as w .

The weights we learn are similar to the idea of propensity scores used in causal inference. However, instead of trying to predict the inclusion of an observation in the treatment group, we are predicting the ‘closeness’ of new groups to groups seen in the training data.

In the second stage of the model, we learn a unique decision tree for each training group k . The predicted outcome y_t for a test data point X_t is then calculated as a linear combination of these K trees, each weighted by its corresponding value in w .

For the first stage of the method, a model like logistic regression or naïve Bayes works well for its interpretable probabilities. In the second stage of the model, any learner can be used, but we focus on decision trees as they strike a good balance between interpretability and predictive performance. **Figure 1** provides an illustration of our proposed method.

Figure 1: (A) Consider grouped data such that each training observation falls into some group (e.g. patients with multiple observations). The test data are similarly structured but come from new groups not seen in the training data. (B) We then construct a classifier that predicts the group that each new observation belongs to, and extract the predicted probabilities of group membership. (C) Finally, we construct independent trees on each group seen in the training set. The final output is a linear combination of the predictions from all of these trees with the probabilities from (B) as weights.

2.2 Implementation

Our weighted sum-of-trees model is implemented in Python. For the base learners, we rely on the scikit-learn implementation of the methods with default parameter values (Pedregosa et al., 2011). The code is publicly available on GitHub at <https://github.com/kmccoy3/weighted-trees>.

3 Results

In this section, we compare the performance of our proposed weighted sum-of-trees method to a GLMM, a standard decision tree, and a random forest on both simulated and real data. We are not able to compare to MERT, as there is no publicly available implementation of this method.

3.1 Simulated Data

3.1.1 Data generation

We construct a continuous response variable y using:

$$y_{i,j} = f(\mathbf{x}_{i,j}) + \mathbf{Z}\boldsymbol{\alpha}_j + \varepsilon,$$

$$i \in \{1, \dots, n\}, \quad j \in \{1, \dots, k\}$$

where \mathbf{Z} is the random effects design matrix, $\boldsymbol{\alpha}_j$ are the random slopes and intercept shared by all observations within a group, and $\varepsilon \sim \mathcal{N}(0, \sigma_\varepsilon^2)$ with $\sigma_\varepsilon = 1$ is a shared noise term. The index i denotes the i th subject within each group. We employ Friedman’s five-dimensional test function (Friedman, 1991) for the fixed effects function f :

$$f(\mathbf{x}_{i,j}) = \sin(\pi x_1 x_2) + 2(x_3 - 0.5)^2 + x_4 + 0.5x_5.$$

This function is a popular benchmark for machine-learning methods as it includes a mix of linear, non-linear, and interaction terms. In order to generate X data with structured correlation, we employ the matrix normal distribution:

$$\mathbf{X} \sim \mathcal{MN}_{K \times p}(\mathbf{M}, \mathbf{U}, \mathbf{V}),$$

where \mathbf{M} is a $(K \times p)$ location matrix, \mathbf{U} is the $(K \times K)$ group covariance matrix, and \mathbf{V} is the $(p \times p)$ feature covariance matrix. We use a $\text{Unif}(-1, 1)$ distribution to generate the entries of \mathbf{M} . The matrix normal distribution allows us the freedom to specify a number of correlation structures between not only features, but also groups in settings with clustered data. We generate n samples from this distribution, resulting in a total of $n \times K$ observations.

We then generate the random effects α_j using the same matrix normal distribution with the same row covariance matrix \mathbf{U} . Taken together, this is equivalent to generating one sample from a matrix normal $\mathcal{MN}_{K \times (p+1)}(\mathbf{0}, \mathbf{U}, \mathbf{V}^*)$, where \mathbf{V}^* is the column covariance matrix specifying the variance structure between the random slopes and intercept. We use $\mathbf{V}^* = \sigma_\alpha \times \mathbf{I}$, where \mathbf{I} is the $(p + 1) \times (p + 1)$ identity matrix. This data generation strategy results in similar random effects for groups that are close in the X space.

3.1.2 Comparative performance

Figure 2 showcases the mean squared error (MSE) across multiple simulation scenarios. The MSE is calculated on test data as $\frac{1}{n_{\text{test}}} \sum_{i=1}^{n_{\text{test}}} (y_i - \hat{y}_i)^2$, where \hat{y}_i is the predicted outcome value for observation i . We considered simulation settings with varying number of groups K and number of observations per group n . We also varied σ_α , which scales the column covariance matrix for the random effects, so larger values of σ_α result in random effects with larger cross-group differences. We include 80% of the groups K in the training data and reserve the remaining 20% as test data, so n_{test} , the total number of observations in the test data, is $0.2 \times n \times K$.

Figure 2: Mean squared error (MSE) over a range of noise values σ_α for settings where $\mathbf{U} = \mathbf{I}$. The scale of the response variable y is standardized. Each boxplot represents MSE values across 20 simulated data sets. Simulations were performed for the settings $n = 10, K = 40$ (left), $n = K = 20$ (center), and $n = 40, K = 10$ (right).

Based on these simulation results, we find that our weighted sum-of-trees method outperforms standard decision trees and becomes competitive with random forest as the magnitude of random effects σ_α becomes larger. Furthermore, we find the cutoff point to be about where the random noise surpasses the common noise, $\sigma_\alpha > \sigma_\epsilon$. This is impressive given that our method does not incorporate bootstrapping of data or random selection of features. It is also fitted with only $0.8 * K$ trees. Interestingly, the decision tree’s performance degrades as the amount of random noise is increased, while LMM’s performance remains more stable across σ_α values.

Next, we conducted a similar experiment, where instead of using $\mathbf{U} = \mathbf{I}$, we generated a unique \mathbf{U} matrix from an inverse-Wishart distribution $\mathcal{W}^{-1}(\mathbf{I}, p+1)$, where $K+1$ is the degrees of freedom and the scale matrix is taken as the $K \times K$ identity matrix \mathbf{I} . We do this to simulate settings where the feature data and the random effects have a similar group covariance structure. As shown in **Figure 3**, the results are much more homogeneous than in the setting with $\mathbf{U} = \mathbf{I}$, though the trends are generally similar. Linear mixed models perform adequately over the range of σ_α values, while decision trees and random forests, which do comparatively well for the settings with smaller σ_α , get progressively worse. Our weighted sum-of-trees method becomes more advantageous relative to traditional decision trees as the random effects grow larger, eventually becoming competitive with random forests. Notably, the scale of **Figure 3** is larger than that of **Figure 2**, as each method performed poorly for some of the simulated data sets.

Figure 3: Mean Squared Error (MSE) of the various methods tested over a range of random noise values, σ_α , for settings where \mathbf{U} is generated from an inverse-Wishart distribution. The scale of the response variable y is standardized. Each boxplot represents MSE values across 20 simulated data sets. Simulations were performed for the settings $n = 10, K = 40$ (left), $n = K = 20$ (center), and $n = 40, K = 10$ (right).

3.2 Real Data Applications

We apply our proposed weighted sum-of-trees method to two external data sets: the Hospital Doctor Patient data set, a synthetic benchmark data set where patients are clustered by doctor, and real data from The Cancer Genome Atlas, where patients are naturally grouped by cancer subtype.

3.2.1 Hospital Doctor Patient data

The Hospital Doctor Patient (HDP) dataset (UCLA: Statistical Consulting Group, 2012) is a synthetic benchmark dataset with a 3-level hierarchy, as implied by the name. It has 8,525 observations of 27 variables. The subject-level observations correspond to patients which are nested within 407 doctors, which are then nested within 35 hospitals. The variables include: age, marriage status, family history of cancer, smoking history, sex, cancer stage, length of stay, white blood count, red blood count, interleukin 6, C-reactive protein, experience of doctor, prestige of medical school, tumor size, CO2 levels, pain, wound, mobility, number of tumors, morphine, remission status, lung capacity, lawsuits, and medicaid status. In addition to these covariates, the hospital ID and doctor ID are also given.

We chose to predict tumor size based on the remaining features. Under the ground truth for this synthetic data, tumor size was generated using age, family history of cancer, length of stay, smoking

history, cancer stage, and the interaction of smoking history \times age. The generative model included a random intercept by doctor ID and a random slope for length of stay by doctor ID. Hospital ID was not used to generate the tumor size outcome.

In applying our proposed method, we considered both hospital and doctor as the grouping variable. For this dataset, we used a 5-fold cross validation split and averaged MSE values of the 5 runs. The resulting MSEs are shown in **Table 1**. LMM achieves the lowest MSE, which makes sense as the generative model was in fact an LMM. However, our proposed weighted sum-of-trees model clearly outperformed a decision tree.

3.2.2 Sarcoma data

Sarcomas represent a heterogeneous family of cancers arising from the connective tissues in the body, including bone, cartilage, muscle, fat, and vasculature. Since sarcomas are rare (less than 1% of adult cancers), sarcoma patients have historically been grouped together in clinical trials. However, there is a strong interest in identifying treatments that may benefit specific subgroups (Katz et al., 2018). In particular, immunotherapy drugs, which have revolutionized treatment for many cancer types but met with mixed results in sarcoma, may benefit patients with immune microenvironments conducive to therapeutic response (Fazel et al., 2023).

Here, we analyzed the data for the sarcoma cohort in The Cancer Genome Atlas (TCGA, Lazar et al., 2017). We attempt to predict leukocyte fraction, which is the proportion of cells that correspond to white blood cells and is a measure of the extent of immune activity in the tumor (Thorsson et al., 2018). Our method is well-suited for this application, as some types of sarcomas have very few observations in the TCGA data set. We can improve predictive accuracy for these less common subtypes by aligning the predictive model for these smaller groups with those in the larger groups with more observations. Moreover, the TCGA data set only encompasses 6 of the most common subtypes of sarcoma, out of more than 100 (Grünewald et al., 2020). Our approach could be used to generate predictions for subjects with rare disease subtypes that are not well characterized in existing data sets.

In the TCGA study, there are samples available for the following sarcoma subtypes: 80 Leiomyosarcoma (LMS), 50 dedifferentiated liposarcoma (DDLPS), 44 undifferentiated pleomorphic sarcoma (UPS), 17 myxofibrosarcoma (MFS), 10 synovial sarcoma (SS), and 5 malignant peripheral nerve sheath tumor (MPNST). Of the 80 LMS patients, there are 53 soft tissue LMS (STLMS) and 27 gynecologic LMS (ULMS). We use the samples from LMS, DDLPS, UPS, and MFS sarcoma types as training data and the samples from SS and MPNST as test data.

For input features, we use demographic features including age at diagnosis and gender. We also include the copy number aberrations of the following genes: JUN, VGLL3, TERT, MAP3K5, UST, CDKN2A, YAP1, CDKN1B, PTPRQ, RB1, TP53, MYOCD, NF1, CCNE1, CEBPA, ZNF552, ATRX, PTEN, DDIT3, CDK4, HMGA2, MDM2, and FRS2. Finally, we also use the number of silent and non-silent mutations per megabase (Mb). We use these features to predict leukocyte fraction.

Our sum-of-trees method outperforms both a decision tree and random forest, however, it does not perform as well as an LMM. This may be because our set of predictors are all demographic and genomic variables known to be relevant to sarcoma. Since they assume sparsity, decision trees and random forests may have a stronger advantage in settings where a larger number of noise features are considered as inputs.

As a demonstration of the interpretability of our approach, we build a random forest on each subtype in the training data. Here, we rely on a random forest, rather than a decision tree, as the base learner within each group, in order to obtain more stable metrics of feature importance. In **Figure 4**, we present the group-specific variable importance and variable interaction plots (VIVI, Inglis et al., 2023). We are also able to plot the relative variable importances and interactions for each subtype. We calculate this as the VIVI plot of one subtype, minus the average of the other subtypes. In **Figure 5**, we show the VIVI plot for the subtypes included only in the test data by applying the weights of our method to the VIVI plots themselves.

Figure 4: The top row (a-e) illustrate the variable importances and variable interactions (VIVI) learned by a random forest model on each sarcoma subtype. The bottom row (f-j) illustrate the relative variable importances of each sarcoma subtype. These were calculated as the subtypes individual VIVI plot, minus the average of the four remaining plots.

Table 1: Mean Squared Error (MSE) of a linear mixed model, decision tree, random forest, and our proposed weighted sum-of-trees method. Data are reported to three significant figures. Best performances for each real dataset are **bolded**. Key: LMM = Linear Mixed Model, HDP = Hospital Doctor Patient

Dataset	LMM	Decision Tree	Random Forest	Sum of Trees
HDP (doctor)	0.634	1.33	0.639	0.677
HDP (hospital)	0.632	1.28	0.636	0.665
TCGA Sarcoma	0.935	1.21	1.07	1.03

Figure 5: Predicted VIVI plots for the two holdout sarcoma types. These were calculated by taking a weighted sum of VIVI plots for the remaining 5 sarcoma types.

4 Conclusions

We find that our sum-of-trees method provides variable improvements over a range of simulation settings. The sum-of-trees method also becomes competitive with random forests, even though the method does not use any bootstrapping of observations or random sampling of features. Overall, our work shows that constructing decision trees and forests can be improved when significant random effects are present without the need for rigid model constraints. In the future, we plan on investigating how this method translates to categorical and survival outputs. Finally, this work opens the door into how the random forest algorithm can be altered to accommodate random effects.

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